

Phenotypic variation in *Xenopus laevis* tadpoles from contrasting climatic regimes is the result of adaptation and plasticity.

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- Abstract:
- Aim:
 1. Investigating the contribution of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation to tadpole morphology
 2. Investigating the contribution of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation on time to metamorphosis
 3. Testing effect on survival

```
#set up the working directory  
setwd ('C:/Users/kruge/Desktop/Paper')
```

```
#Packages needed  
install.packages("rmarkdown")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("bestNormalize")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("xlsx")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("lmerTest")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("MuMIn")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("DHARMA")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("survival")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages("coxme")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

```
install.packages ("performance")
```

```
## Installing package into 'C:/Users/kruge/AppData/Local/R/win-library/4.2'  
## (as 'lib' is unspecified)
```

Abstract:

Phenotypic variations between populations often correlate with climatic variables. Determining the presence of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation of a species to different environments over a large spatial scale can provide insight on the persistence of a species across its range. Amphibians, and especially their larvae, are good models for studies of phenotypic variation as they are especially sensitive to their immediate environment. Few studies have attempted to determine the mechanisms that drive phenotypic variation between populations of a single amphibian species over a large spatial scale especially across contrasting climatic regimes. The African clawed frog, *Xenopus laevis*, occurs in two regions with contrasting rainfall regimes in southern Africa. We hypothesise that the phenotypic variation of life- history traits of *X. laevis* tadpoles emerges from a combination of plastic and genetic responses. We predict plasticity to allow the development of tadpoles from both regions in each environment. We also predict local adaptation of larval traits to drive the differentiation of reaction norms between populations and lower survival in tadpoles raised away from their home environment. We measured growth, time to metamorphosis, and survival in a reciprocal transplant experiment using outdoor mesocosms. Supporting our prediction, we found that the measured variation of all traits was explained by both adaptation and plasticity. However, the reaction norms differed between populations suggesting adaptive and asymmetric plasticity. All tadpoles experienced lower survival when translocated, but only translocated tadpoles from the winter rainfall region matched survival of local tadpoles.

Aim:

We investigated the relative contribution of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation in the larval development of *X. laevis* originating from different climatic regimes in southern Africa.

1. Investigating the contribution of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation to tadpole morphology

Morphological variation- We measured the morphology of larval individuals at NF stage 45 – 57. The sample size for climax individuals (NF stage 58 – 65) was too small to be included in statistical treatment after the 10 week experimental period. To assess the effect of experimental venue (summer or winter rainfall region) and population locality (summer-or winter rainfall) on larval morphology we performed a PCA using linear measurements (Fig. S2). The first principal component accounted for 94% of variation (± 2.16 SD) (Table S1). Loadings were positive for head width (0.442), SVL (0.450), maximum body depth (0.453), tail depth (0.448) and tail length (0.443). Loadings were similar if we ran this for the individual populations. We retained only the first PCA axis in our analysis as it represents a global measurement of body size. Using the lme4 R package (Bates et al. 2015), linear mixed models were utilized with body size (PC1) as the response variable, and experimental venue, population locality, their interaction and NF stage (discrete variable) and its interaction with experimental venue and population locality as fixed effects. Clutch, nested within collection site, was considered as a random effect. All variables (measurements for PC1) were tested for normality and normalised with the bestNormalize R package (Peterson and Cavanaugh 2019). The best transformation informed by bestNormalize was Ordered Quantile transformation. PC1 was plotted using ggplot2 R package (Wickham 2009).

```
#Import data
Tadpole1=read.table('Tadpole.txt',header=T)
names(Tadpole1)
```

```
## [1] "Experimentalvenue" "Origin"          "Treatment"
## [4] "Site"              "Clutch"         "Clutchx"
## [7] "Tadpole"          "Week"          "tadpoleID"
## [10] "Mesocosm"         "Date"          "Fulllength"
## [13] "Maximumbodydepth" "Snoutventlength" "Taillength"
## [16] "Maxtaildepth"    "Headwidth"     "Femur"
## [19] "Totalleglength"  "Stage"         "Stagecategory"
```

```
attach(Tadpole1)
```

```
#Defining variables - multiple predictors
experimentalvenue1<-as.factor(Experimentalvenue)#categorical factor
summary(experimentalvenue1) #fixed effect
```

```
## Potchefstroom Stellenbosch
##           346           461
```

```
origin1<-as.factor(Origin)#categorical factor
summary(origin1) #fixed effect
```

```
## Potchefstroom Stellenbosch
##           396           411
```

```
treatment1<-as.factor(Treatment)#categorical factor
summary(treatment1) #Interaction
```

```
## PP PS SP SS
## 189 157 207 254
```

```
#PS- Potchefstroom experimental venue, Stellenbosch origin
#PP- Potchefstroom experimental venue, Potchefstroom origin
#SP- Stellenbosch experimental venue, Potchefstroom origin
#SS- Stellenbosch experimental venue, Stellenbosch origin

summary(Week) #fixed effect
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  0.00    2.00    4.00    4.45    7.00   10.00
```

```
summary(Stage) #fixed effect
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  45.00   47.00   49.00   49.93   53.00   57.00
```

```
#Testing for colinearity:
#check data distribution
#to check data distribution we use the shapiro.test
shapiro.test(Week) #distribution is normal
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Week
## W = 0.95704, p-value = 1.277e-14
```

```
shapiro.test(Stage) #not normal
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  Stage
## W = 0.92951, p-value < 2.2e-16
```

```
#Null hypothesis: Data is not different from normal distributed data
# p-value >0.05: Normally distributed - Accept null hypothesis
# p-value <0.05: Not normally distributed - Reject null hypothesis

#data are not normally distributed for stage
#so a spearman's rank correlation test is the best option in this case

cor.test(Week, Stage, method="spearman")
```

```
## Warning in cor.test.default(Week, Stage, method = "spearman"): Cannot compute
## exact p-value with ties
```

```
##
## Spearman's rank correlation rho
##
## data: Week and Stage
## S = 44807067, p-value < 2.2e-16
## alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
## sample estimates:
##      rho
## 0.4884621
```

*#According to the spearman correlation test "Stage" and "Week" is correlated,
#Thus, We cannot add both week and stage due to colinearity.*

```
site1<-as.factor(Site)
summary(site1) #Random effect
```

```
## BT CP JH KM LP PS
## 159 97 113 201 115 122
```

```
clutch1<-as.factor(Clutchx)
summary(clutch1) #Nested within site
```

```
## BT1 BT2 CP1 CP2 JH1 JH2 JH3 KM1 KM2 KM3 LP1 LP2 LP3 PS1 PS2 PS3
## 77 82 48 49 45 33 35 90 61 50 43 42 30 42 32 48
```

```
# Transforming response variables
library(bestNormalize)
#SnoutventLength
shapiro.test(Snoutventlength)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: Snoutventlength
## W = 0.96088, p-value = 7.39e-14
```

```
hist(Snoutventlength)
```

Histogram of Snoutventlength


```
bestNormalize(Snoutventlength, standardize= TRUE, allow_orderNorm=TRUE,
  allow_lambert_s = FALSE, allow_lambert_h = FALSE,
  out_of_sample = TRUE, cluster = NULL, k = 10, r = 5,
  loo = FALSE, warn = TRUE, quiet = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(standardize = TRUE, warn = TRUE, x = c(3.573, 3.108, : Ties in data,
Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
## Best Normalizing transformation with 807 Observations
## Estimated Normality Statistics (Pearson P / df, lower => more normal):
## - arcsinh(x): 2.1112
## - Box-Cox: 1.5758
## - Center+scale: 2.2067
## - Exp(x): 78.7226
## - Log_b(x+a): 2.127
## - orderNorm (ORQ): 1.0846
## - sqrt(x + a): 1.4882
## - Yeo-Johnson: 1.5832
## Estimation method: Out-of-sample via CV with 10 folds and 5 repeats
##
## Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
## orderNorm Transformation with 807 nonmissing obs and ties
## - 799 unique values
## - Original quantiles:
##   0%   25%   50%   75%  100%
## 2.828 7.268 10.788 16.473 28.219
```

```
orderNorm_SVL <- orderNorm(Snoutventlength)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(Snoutventlength): Ties in data, Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
pSVL <- predict(orderNorm_SVL)  
summary(pSVL)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.   
## -3.2297 -0.6735  0.0000  0.0000  0.6735  3.2297
```

```
shapiro.test(pSVL)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  pSVL  
## W = 0.99994, p-value = 1
```

```
#p-value= 1 (tadpoles)  
hist(pSVL)
```



```
shapiro.test(Maximumbodydepth)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Maximumbodydepth  
## W = 0.94651, p-value < 2.2e-16
```

```
hist(Maximumbodydepth)
```

Histogram of Maximumbodydepth


```
bestNormalize(Maximumbodydepth, standardize= TRUE, allow_orderNorm=TRUE,  
              allow_lambert_s = FALSE, allow_lambert_h = FALSE,  
              out_of_sample = TRUE, cluster = NULL, k = 10, r = 5,  
              loo = FALSE, warn = TRUE, quiet = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(standardize = TRUE, warn = TRUE, x = c(1.564, 1.565, : Ties in data,  
Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
## Best Normalizing transformation with 807 Observations
## Estimated Normality Statistics (Pearson P / df, lower => more normal):
## - arcsinh(x): 1.4032
## - Box-Cox: 1.2966
## - Center+scale: 2.6038
## - Exp(x): 57.4847
## - Log_b(x+a): 1.4035
## - orderNorm (ORQ): 1.2394
## - sqrt(x + a): 1.4783
## - Yeo-Johnson: 1.3279
## Estimation method: Out-of-sample via CV with 10 folds and 5 repeats
##
## Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
## orderNorm Transformation with 807 nonmissing obs and ties
## - 769 unique values
## - Original quantiles:
##   0%    25%    50%    75%   100%
## 1.501  3.460  5.148  7.704 13.313
```

```
#Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
```

```
#orderNorm Transformation
```

```
orderNorm_Bodydepth <- orderNorm(Maximumbodydepth)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(Maximumbodydepth): Ties in data, Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
pMaximumbodydepth <- predict(orderNorm_Bodydepth)
summary(pMaximumbodydepth)
```

```
##      Min.   1st Qu.   Median     Mean   3rd Qu.     Max.
## -3.229710 -0.673516  0.000000  0.000024  0.673516  3.229710
```

```
shapiro.test(pMaximumbodydepth)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  pMaximumbodydepth
## W = 0.99991, p-value = 1
```

```
#p-value= 1 (tadpoles)
hist(pMaximumbodydepth)
```

Histogram of pMaximumbodydepth


```
shapiro.test(Headwidth)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Headwidth  
## W = 0.95864, p-value = 2.611e-14
```

```
hist(Headwidth)
```

Histogram of Headwidth


```
bestNormalize(Headwidth, standardize= TRUE, allow_orderNorm=TRUE,
              allow_lambert_s = FALSE, allow_lambert_h = FALSE,
              out_of_sample = TRUE, cluster = NULL, k = 10, r = 5,
              loo = FALSE, warn = TRUE, quiet = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(standardize = TRUE, warn = TRUE, x = c(1.963, 2.04, : Ties in data, N
normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
## Best Normalizing transformation with 807 Observations
## Estimated Normality Statistics (Pearson P / df, lower => more normal):
## - arcsinh(x): 1.6697
## - Box-Cox: 1.4988
## - Center+scale: 2.1745
## - Exp(x): 56.341
## - Log_b(x+a): 1.6994
## - orderNorm (ORQ): 1.1582
## - sqrt(x + a): 1.4793
## - Yeo-Johnson: 1.473
## Estimation method: Out-of-sample via CV with 10 folds and 5 repeats
##
## Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
## orderNorm Transformation with 807 nonmissing obs and ties
## - 762 unique values
## - Original quantiles:
##   0%   25%   50%   75%  100%
## 1.119 3.948 5.434 7.906 14.368
```

```
#Based off these, bestNormalize chose:  
#orderNorm Transformation  
  
orderNorm_Headwidth <- orderNorm(Headwidth)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(Headwidth): Ties in data, Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
pHeadwidth <- predict(orderNorm_Headwidth)  
  
shapiro.test(pHeadwidth)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  pHeadwidth  
## W = 0.99994, p-value = 1
```

```
#p-value = 1 (tadpoles)  
hist(pHeadwidth)
```

Histogram of pHeadwidth


```
shapiro.test(Taillength)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  Taillength  
## W = 0.94748, p-value = 2.482e-16
```

```
hist(Taillength)
```

Histogram of Taillength


```
bestNormalize(Taillength, standardize= TRUE, allow_orderNorm=TRUE,  
              allow_lambert_s = FALSE, allow_lambert_h = FALSE,  
              out_of_sample = TRUE, cluster = NULL, k = 10, r = 5,  
              loo = FALSE, warn = TRUE, quiet = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in bestNormalize(Taillength, standardize = TRUE, allow_orderNorm = TRUE, : boxcox  
did not work; Error in estimate_boxcox_lambda(x, ...) : x must be positive
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(standardize = TRUE, warn = TRUE, x = c(5.267, 5.532, : Ties in data,  
Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
## Best Normalizing transformation with 807 Observations
## Estimated Normality Statistics (Pearson P / df, lower => more normal):
## - arcsinh(x): 1.9901
## - Center+scale: 3.1325
## - Exp(x): 89.9375
## - Log_b(x+a): 2.6145
## - orderNorm (ORQ): 1.1693
## - sqrt(x + a): 1.8031
## - Yeo-Johnson: 1.7177
## Estimation method: Out-of-sample via CV with 10 folds and 5 repeats
##
## Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
## orderNorm Transformation with 807 nonmissing obs and ties
## - 801 unique values
## - Original quantiles:
##   0%    25%   50%   75%  100%
## 0.000  9.677 15.750 24.938 45.566
```

```
#Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
#orderNorm Transformation
```

```
orderNorm_Taillength <- orderNorm(Taillength)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(Taillength): Ties in data, Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
pTaillength <- predict(orderNorm_Taillength)
summary(pTaillength)
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## -3.2297 -0.6735  0.0000  0.0000  0.6735  3.2297
```

```
shapiro.test(pTaillength)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  pTaillength
## W = 0.99994, p-value = 1
```

```
#p-value = 1
hist(pTaillength)
```

Histogram of pTaillength


```
shapiro.test(Maxtaildepth)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: Maxtaildepth  
## W = 0.9134, p-value < 2.2e-16
```

```
hist(Maxtaildepth)
```

Histogram of Maxtaildepth


```
bestNormalize(Maxtaildepth, standardize= TRUE, allow_orderNorm=TRUE,
              allow_lambert_s = FALSE, allow_lambert_h = FALSE,
              out_of_sample = TRUE, cluster = NULL, k = 10, r = 5,
              loo = FALSE, warn = TRUE, quiet = FALSE)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(standardize = TRUE, warn = TRUE, x = c(1.124, 1.079, : Ties in data,
Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
## Best Normalizing transformation with 807 Observations
## Estimated Normality Statistics (Pearson P / df, lower => more normal):
## - arcsinh(x): 1.8232
## - Box-Cox: 1.7987
## - Center+scale: 4.1385
## - Exp(x): 50.1661
## - Log_b(x+a): 1.7194
## - orderNorm (ORQ): 1.2524
## - sqrt(x + a): 2.4861
## - Yeo-Johnson: 1.896
## Estimation method: Out-of-sample via CV with 10 folds and 5 repeats
##
## Based off these, bestNormalize chose:
## orderNorm Transformation with 807 nonmissing obs and ties
## - 733 unique values
## - Original quantiles:
##   0%   25%   50%   75%  100%
## 0.788 1.930 3.181 5.482 10.465
```

```
#Based off these, bestNormalize chose:  
#orderNorm Transformation  
  
orderNorm_Taildepth <- orderNorm(Maxtaildepth)
```

```
## Warning in orderNorm(Maxtaildepth): Ties in data, Normal distribution not guaranteed
```

```
pTaildepth <- predict(orderNorm_Taildepth)  
summary(pTaildepth)
```

```
##      Min.   1st Qu.   Median     Mean   3rd Qu.    Max.     
## -3.229710 -0.673516  0.000000 -0.000002  0.673516  3.229710
```

```
shapiro.test(pTaildepth)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  pTaildepth  
## W = 0.99993, p-value = 1
```

```
#p-value = 1  
hist(pTaildepth)
```

Histogram of pTaildepth


```
# Performing PCA for tadpole variables.
tadpolepca<- cbind(pSVL, pMaximumbodydepth, pHeadwidth, pTaildepth, pTaillength)

tadpca1=prcomp(tadpolepca)
summary(tadpca1) #PC1 describes 94% of variance
```

```
## Importance of components:
##
##          PC1      PC2      PC3      PC4      PC5
## Standard deviation  2.1667 0.34861 0.28827 0.2469 0.19462
## Proportion of Variance 0.9393 0.02432 0.01663 0.0122 0.00758
## Cumulative Proportion 0.9393 0.96359 0.98022 0.9924 1.00000
```

```
tadpca1 #ALL loadings are positive
```

```
## Standard deviations (1, .., p=5):
## [1] 2.1666730 0.3486092 0.2882735 0.2469442 0.1946207
##
## Rotation (n x k) = (5 x 5):
##
##          PC1      PC2      PC3      PC4      PC5
## pSVL      0.4504192 -0.18026786  0.4309840 -0.5060069 -0.56818650
## pMaximumbodydepth 0.4532056 -0.07464077  0.2679878 -0.2502309  0.80907384
## pHeadwidth  0.4418395 -0.68580393 -0.5071509  0.2716527 -0.05876709
## pTaildepth  0.4479747  0.31381140  0.3753909  0.7389523 -0.11778032
## pTaillength  0.4425198  0.62699891 -0.5867836 -0.2479835 -0.07237296
```

```
biplot(tadpca1)
```



```
tadpca1scores<-predict(tadpca1)

taddataset <- cbind(Tadpole1, tadpca1scores) #combine datasets
library(xlsx)
write.xlsx(taddataset, "C:/Users/kruge/Desktop/Paper/mydata.xlsx")

names(taddataset)
```

```
## [1] "Experimentalvenue" "Origin"          "Treatment"
## [4] "Site"               "Clutch"         "Clutchx"
## [7] "Tadpole"           "Week"          "tadpoleID"
## [10] "Mesocosm"          "Date"          "Fulllength"
## [13] "Maximumbodydepth" "Snoutventlength" "Taillength"
## [16] "Maxtaildepth"     "Headwidth"     "Femur"
## [19] "Totalleglength"  "Stage"         "Stagecategory"
## [22] "PC1"             "PC2"          "PC3"
## [25] "PC4"             "PC5"
```

```
#Model selection for variables.
#PC1
#Use the *taddataset* for the analysis.
library(lmerTest)
```

```
## Loading required package: lme4
```

```
## Loading required package: Matrix
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'lmerTest'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:lme4':
##
## lmer
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:stats':
##
## step
```

```
#Global model
Stage1<-as.factor(Stage)

PC1a<- lmer(PC1 ~ experimentalvenue1*Stage1 + origin1*Stage1 + experimentalvenue1*origin1 + (
1|Site/Clutchx),na.action = "na.pass", data = taddataset)

library(MuMIn)
dredge(PC1a)
```

```
## Warning in dredge(PC1a): comparing models fitted by REML
```

```
## Fixed term is "(Intercept)"
```

```
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
```

	(Intercept) <dbl>	experimentalvenue1 <fct>	origin1 <fct>	Stag... <fct>	experimentalvenue1:origin1 <fct>
56	-4.447831323	+	+	+	NA
64	-4.398735229	+	+	+	+
32	-4.253196716	+	+	+	+
22	-4.376060551	+	NA	+	NA
24	-4.371482451	+	+	+	NA
16	-3.653609266	+	+	+	+
48	-3.761396644	+	+	+	+
6	-3.811226586	+	NA	+	NA
5	-3.940789270	NA	NA	+	NA
8	-3.842626834	+	+	+	NA

1-10 of 18 rows | 1-6 of 13 columns

Previous **1** 2 Next

```
PC1best<- lmer(PC1 ~ experimentalvenue1 + origin1 + Stage1 + experimentalvenue1*Stage1 + origin1*Stage1 + experimentalvenue1*origin1 + (1|Site/Clutchx),na.action = "na.pass", data = taddataset)
summary(PC1best)
```

```

## Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method [
## lmerModLmerTest]
## Formula: PC1 ~ experimentalvenue1 + origin1 + Stage1 + experimentalvenue1 *
##   Stage1 + origin1 * Stage1 + experimentalvenue1 * origin1 +
##   (1 | Site/Clutchx)
##   Data: taddataset
##
## REML criterion at convergence: 1701.8
##
## Scaled residuals:
##   Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -3.1322 -0.5899 -0.0244  0.6476  4.8903
##
## Random effects:
##   Groups      Name          Variance Std.Dev.
##   Clutchx:Site (Intercept) 0.071021 0.26650
##   Site         (Intercept) 0.004023 0.06343
##   Residual                0.444184 0.66647
## Number of obs: 807, groups: Clutchx:Site, 16; Site, 6
##
## Fixed effects:
##
##                                     Estimate Std. Error    df
## (Intercept)                        -4.3987     0.1966  27.4166
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch       0.5903     0.2248 408.0042
## origin1Stellenbosch                  0.1290     0.2682  21.6036
## Stage146                             0.5691     0.2569 761.8650
## Stage147                             2.4985     0.1987 761.6660
## Stage148                             3.3478     0.2429 757.0721
## Stage149                             4.8340     0.2300 758.1365
## Stage150                             4.9687     0.2218 760.0357
## Stage151                             5.7268     0.2145 759.5259
## Stage152                             6.1683     0.2311 763.7290
## Stage153                             6.4925     0.2507 759.3723
## Stage154                             6.9000     0.2184 761.8254
## Stage155                             7.7527     0.2140 763.4618
## Stage156                             8.3857     0.2442 766.2484
## Stage157                             8.3723     0.2608 761.4181
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage146  0.4428     0.2698 763.5018
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage147 -0.4501     0.2411 763.7320
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage148 -0.5728     0.2818 762.6974
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage149 -1.2986     0.2663 762.9486
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage150 -1.0240     0.2753 763.2687
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage151 -1.1349     0.2703 761.6321
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage152 -1.4997     0.2855 764.5126
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage153 -1.4545     0.3108 763.6201
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage154 -1.5411     0.2887 759.8401
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage155 -1.8905     0.2919 766.2861
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage156 -1.8947     0.3396 766.3944
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage157 -1.5495     0.4050 765.4992
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage146           0.4301     0.2649 760.0957
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage147           0.1335     0.2402 762.9946
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage148          -0.1997     0.2675 762.3100
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage149          -0.2333     0.2529 764.6061
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage150          -0.2962     0.2784 763.9963
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage151          -0.2647     0.2780 762.6439

```

```

## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage152          -0.1134    0.2980 763.7059
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage153          -0.4407    0.3135 761.2705
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage154          -0.5630    0.2982 762.1729
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage155          -1.0154    0.2944 762.6073
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage156          -1.4317    0.3373 764.2108
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage157          -0.5305    0.4066 760.8970
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:origin1Stellenbosch  0.2050    0.1753 79.9167
##
##                                     t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)                         -22.371 < 2e-16 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch        2.626 0.008972 **
## origin1Stellenbosch                   0.481 0.635249
## Stage146                              2.215 0.027057 *
## Stage147                             12.574 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage148                             13.783 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage149                             21.014 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage150                             22.397 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage151                             26.701 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage152                             26.696 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage153                             25.901 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage154                             31.595 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage155                             36.221 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage156                             34.345 < 2e-16 ***
## Stage157                             32.104 < 2e-16 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage146    1.641 0.101110
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage147   -1.867 0.062276 .
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage148   -2.033 0.042404 *
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage149   -4.876 1.32e-06 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage150   -3.720 0.000214 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage151   -4.199 3.00e-05 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage152   -5.253 1.94e-07 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage153   -4.679 3.41e-06 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage154   -5.338 1.24e-07 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage155   -6.475 1.69e-10 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage156   -5.580 3.34e-08 ***
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:Stage157   -3.826 0.000141 ***
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage146            1.623 0.104901
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage147            0.556 0.578528
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage148           -0.746 0.455643
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage149           -0.923 0.356468
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage150          -1.064 0.287729
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage151          -0.952 0.341414
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage152          -0.381 0.703653
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage153          -1.406 0.160172
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage154          -1.888 0.059380 .
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage155          -3.449 0.000593 ***
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage156          -4.245 2.46e-05 ***
## origin1Stellenbosch:Stage157          -1.305 0.192380
## experimentalvenue1Stellenbosch:origin1Stellenbosch  1.170 0.245570
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

##
## Correlation matrix not shown by default, as p = 40 > 12.
## Use print(x, correlation=TRUE) or
##     vcov(x)         if you need it

```

```
#Ls_mean_square
xx<- ls_means(PC1best, pairwise = T)
View(xx)
```

```
#calculate R2
library (performance)
r2 (PC1best)
```

```
## # R2 for Mixed Models
##
## Conditional R2: 0.906
## Marginal R2: 0.890
```

```
library(DHARMa)
```

```
## This is DHARMa 0.4.5. For overview type '?DHARMa'. For recent changes, type news(package = 'DHARMa')
```

```
rr=simulateResiduals(PC1best) ### simulate residuals
plotResiduals(rr) ### qqplot simulated vs observed
```



```
testResiduals(rr)###test qqplot
```



```
## $uniformity
##
## Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
## data: simulationOutput$scaledResiduals
## D = 0.039732, p-value = 0.1564
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
##
##
## $dispersion
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.92764, p-value = 0.288
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
##
##
## $outliers
##
## DHARMA outlier test based on exact binomial test with approximate
## expectations
##
## data: simulationOutput
## outliers at both margin(s) = 6, observations = 807, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: true probability of success is not equal to 0.007968127
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.002733238 0.016112049
## sample estimates:
## frequency of outliers (expected: 0.00796812749003984 )
##                                0.007434944
```

```
## $uniformity
##
## Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
## data: simulationOutput$scaledResiduals
## D = 0.039732, p-value = 0.1564
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
##
##
## $dispersion
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 0.92764, p-value = 0.288
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
##
##
## $outliers
##
## DHARMA outlier test based on exact binomial test with approximate
## expectations
##
## data: simulationOutput
## outliers at both margin(s) = 6, observations = 807, p-value = 1
## alternative hypothesis: true probability of success is not equal to 0.007968127
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.002733238 0.016112049
## sample estimates:
## frequency of outliers (expected: 0.00796812749003984 )
##                                0.007434944
```

```
plotQQunif(rr, testUniformity = T) ### plot
```

QQ plot residuals


```
testDispersion(rr,plot=T) ### test
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated

Simulated values, red line = fitted model. p -value (two.sided) = 0.288

```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
## simulated  
##  
## data: simulationOutput  
## dispersion = 0.92764, p-value = 0.288  
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
```

```
hist(residuals(PC1best))
```



```
shapiro.test(residuals(PC1best))
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: residuals(PC1best)  
## W = 0.99498, p-value = 0.009352
```

```
detach(Tadpole1)
```

2. Investigating the contribution of phenotypic plasticity and local adaptation on time to metamorphosis

Time to metamorphosis - To determine the time to metamorphosis we counted the number of collected individuals that underwent a transition event from larvae (NF stage 45-57) to metamorphic climax (NF stage 58-65). We conducted a Cox proportional hazards analysis on transition between larvae and metamorphic climax stages using the `coxme` (Therneau 2020a) and `survival` (Therneau 2020b) R packages. The week when a transition occurred between larvae and climax was considered as the response variable, and experimental venue and population locality as fixed effects and clutch nested within collection site as random effects. For all analyses, we selected the best fitting model using corrected Akaike information criterion (AICc) according to parsimony (Burnham and Anderson 2002). Multi-model inference (model averaging) was carried out to account for model selection uncertainty between the top models ($\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) using the `MuMIn` package (Barton 2020). Model coefficients were subsequently averaged across the set of top models and the resulting averaged coefficients were used for predictions. If the top model was equal ($\Delta\text{AICc} < 2$) to the null model, the null model was not rejected. The chosen model was then used to calculate the least square means of interactions using the `lsmeans` R package (Lenth 2016). Model diagnostics were carried out using the `DHARMA` R package (Hartig 2019). All analyses were carried out using the statistical software R 3.4.1 (R Core Team 2018).

```
Climax=read.table('Climax.txt',header=T)
names(Climax)
```

```
## [1] "num"           "Experimentalvenue" "Origin"
## [4] "Treatment"     "Site"              "Clutch"
## [7] "Clutchx"       "Tadpole"           "Week"
## [10] "Weeknr"        "tadpoleID"         "Mesocosm"
## [13] "Date"          "Stage"              "Stagecategory"
## [16] "climax"
```

```
attach(Climax)

#defining variables
experimentalvenue2<-as.factor(Experimentalvenue)

Origin2<-as.factor(Origin)
summary(Origin2)
```

```
## Potchefstroom Stellenbosch
##           419           428
```

```
treatment2<-as.factor(Treatment)
summary(treatment2) #fixed effect
```

```
## PP PS SP SS
## 202 172 217 256
```

```
summary(Weeknr) #fixed effect
```

```
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   1.00   3.00   5.00   5.58   8.00  11.00
```

```
summary(Week)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##      0.00    2.00    4.00    4.58    7.00   10.00
```

```
site2<-as.factor(Site)
summary(site2) #Random effect
```

```
##  BT  CP  JH  KM  LP  PS
## 165  99 124 205 123 131
```

```
clutch2<-as.factor(Clutchx)
summary(clutch2) #Nested within site
```

```
## BT1 BT2 CP1 CP2 JH1 JH2 JH3 KM1 KM2 KM3 LP1 LP2 LP3 PS1 PS2 PS3
##  78  87  50  49  45  42  37  94  61  50  43  45  35  46  36  49
```

```
summary(climax)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
## 0.000000 0.000000 0.000000 0.04723 0.000000 1.000000
```

```
library(survival)
mysurv2<- Surv(Week, climax)
plot(mysurv2)
```



```
#Kaplan-Meier non-parametric analysis by group (fixed effect) without random effect to create plot
```

```
kmsurvival2 <- survfit((mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2)
summary(kmsurvival2)
```

```
## Call: survfit(formula = (mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2)
```

```
##
```

```
##          experimentalvenue2=Potchefstroom
```

```
## time n.risk n.event survival std.err lower 95% CI upper 95% CI
```

```
##    6   116     8   0.931  0.0235    0.886    0.978
```

```
##    7    72    14   0.750  0.0474    0.663    0.849
```

```
##    8    31     6   0.605  0.0655    0.489    0.748
```

```
##
```

```
##          experimentalvenue2=Stellenbosch
```

```
## time n.risk n.event survival std.err lower 95% CI upper 95% CI
```

```
##    5   262     2   0.992 0.00538    0.982    1.000
```

```
##    7   162     4   0.968 0.01319    0.942    0.994
```

```
##    8   113     1   0.959 0.01561    0.929    0.990
```

```
##    9    74     2   0.933 0.02361    0.888    0.981
```

```
##   10    34     3   0.851 0.05025    0.758    0.955
```

```
plot(kmsurvival2, xlab = "Week", ylab = "Prometamorphosis to climax transition", col= rainbow
(4, alpha = 1),mark = 3)
```



```
#Model selection
```

```
library(coxme)
```

```
## Loading required package: bdsmatrix
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'bdsmatrix'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:base':
##
## backsolve
```

```
## Registered S3 methods overwritten by 'coxme':
## method from
## formula.coxme MuMIn
## logLik.coxme MuMIn
## logLik.lmekin MuMIn
```

```
clim1<-coxme((mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2*Origin2+(1|site2/clutch2), data=Climax, na.action
= "na.pass")
```

```
dredge(clim1)
```

experimentalvenue2 <fct>	Origin2 <fct>	experimentalvenue2:Origin2 <fct>	df <int>	logLik <dbl>	AICc <dbl>	
4 +	+	NA	12	-158.8823	343.6830	0.
2 +	NA	NA	12	-158.9720	343.9598	0.
8 +	+	+	12	-159.1780	344.2958	0.
3 NA	+	NA	11	-173.9525	372.1329	28.
1 NA	NA	NA	11	-174.1752	372.6599	28.

5 rows | 1-8 of 9 columns

```
#Three models chosen, therefore model averaging is necessary
```

```
#Model averaging:
```

```
dredge.gm <-dredge(clim1)
dredge.gm
```

experimentalvenue2 <fct>	Origin2 <fct>	experimentalvenue2:Origin2 <fct>	df <int>	logLik <dbl>	AICc <dbl>	
4 +	+	NA	12	-158.8823	343.6830	0.
2 +	NA	NA	12	-158.9720	343.9598	0.
8 +	+	+	12	-159.1780	344.2958	0.
3 NA	+	NA	11	-173.9525	372.1329	28.
1 NA	NA	NA	11	-174.1752	372.6599	28.

5 rows | 1-8 of 9 columns

```
top.models <- get.models(dredge.gm, delta < 2)
summary(top.models)
```

```
##   Length Class Mode
## 4 20      coxme list
## 2 20      coxme list
## 8 20      coxme list
```

```
top.models.avg <- (model.avg(top.models))
top.models.avg
```

```
##
## Call:
## model.avg(object = top.models)
##
## Component models:
## '12' '1' '123'
##
## Coefficients:
##      experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -3.606632                -0.5279010
## subset              -3.606632                -0.7926738
##      experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -0.6417624
## subset              -2.2727648
```

```
summary(top.models.avg)
```

```
##
## Call:
## model.avg(object = top.models)
##
## Component model call:
## coxme(formula = (mysurv2) ~ <3 unique rhs>, data = Climax, na.action =
##     na.pass)
##
## Component models:
##      df logLik  AICc delta weight
## 12 12.75 -153.95 343.68 0.00 0.38
## 1 12.80 -153.99 343.96 0.28 0.33
## 123 12.76 -154.33 344.30 0.61 0.28
##
## Term codes:
##      experimentalvenue2      Origin2
##                1                2
## experimentalvenue2:Origin2
##                3
##
## Model-averaged coefficients:
## (full average)
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch -3.6066 1.0242 3.521
## Origin2Stellenbosch -0.5279 1.1104 0.475
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch -0.6418 1.2945 0.496
##
##              Pr(>|z|)
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch 0.000429 ***
## Origin2Stellenbosch 0.634500
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch 0.620077
##
## (conditional average)
##
##              Estimate Std. Error z value
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch -3.6066 1.0242 3.521
## Origin2Stellenbosch -0.7927 1.2813 0.619
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch -2.2728 1.4927 1.523
##
##              Pr(>|z|)
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch 0.000429 ***
## Origin2Stellenbosch 0.536134
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch 0.127856
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

#The 'subset' (or 'conditional') average only averages over the models where the parameter appears. An alternative, the 'full' average assumes that a variable is included in every model, but in some models the corresponding coefficient (and its respective variance) is set to zero. Unlike the 'subset average', it does not have a tendency of biasing the value away from zero. The 'full' average is a type of shrinkage estimator, and for variables with a weak relationship to the response it is smaller than 'subset' estimators

```
coef(top.models.avg)
```

```
##          experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch
##                               -3.6066318
##          Origin2Stellenbosch
##                               -0.7926738
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch
##                               -2.2727648
```

```
confint(top.models.avg, level= 0.95)
```

```
##                               2.5 %    97.5 %
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch -5.613981 -1.5992828
## Origin2Stellenbosch           -3.303891  1.7185429
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch -5.198351  0.6528218
```

```
formula(top.models.avg)
```

```
## (mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2 + Origin2 + experimentalvenue2:Origin2
```

```
print(top.models.avg)
```

```
##
## Call:
## model.avg(object = top.models)
##
## Component models:
## '12' '1' '123'
##
## Coefficients:
##          experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -3.606632                -0.5279010
## subset              -3.606632                -0.7926738
##          experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -0.6417624
## subset              -2.2727648
```

```
##
## Call:
## model.avg(object = top.models)
##
## Component models:
## '12' '1' '123'
##
## Coefficients:
##          experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -3.606632                -0.5279010
## subset              -3.606632                -0.7926738
##          experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch:Origin2Stellenbosch
## full                -0.6417624
## subset              -2.2727648
```

```
bestclim<-coxme((mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2 +(1|site2/clutch2), data=Climax, na.action =
"na.pass")
summary(bestclim)
```

```
## Cox mixed-effects model fit by maximum likelihood
## Data: Climax
## events, n = 40, 847
## Iterations= 7 41
##              NULL Integrated   Fitted
## Log-likelihood -209.5992 -173.9607 -153.9899
##
##              Chisq  df          p  AIC  BIC
## Integrated loglik  71.28  3.0 2.2204e-15 65.28 60.21
## Penalized loglik 111.22 12.8 0.0000e+00 85.63 64.02
##
## Model: (mysurv2) ~ experimentalvenue2 + (1 | site2/clutch2)
## Fixed coefficients
##              coef exp(coef) se(coef)      z      p
## experimentalvenue2Stellenbosch -3.992815 0.01844771 0.9109223 -4.38 1.2e-05
##
## Random effects
## Group      Variable      Std Dev Variance
## site2/clutch2 (Intercept) 1.791010 3.207716
## site2      (Intercept) 1.146301 1.314005
```

```
detach(Climax)
```

3. Testing effect on survival

Variation in survival - We removed a total of 50 individuals from the mesocosms owing to our weekly sampling for the morphological study. Thus, the number of surviving individuals at the end of the experiment was tallied out of 150. We modelled the probability of surviving until the end of the experiment in mesocosms using generalised binomial mixed models with fate (1 = survived, 0 = died) as the response variable, experimental venue and population locality as fixed effects, and clutch nested within collection site as a random effect.

```
Overallsurvival <- read.table('Survival.txt',header=T)
names(Overallsurvival)
```

```
## [1] "Experimentalvenue" "Origin"      "Mesocosm"
## [4] "Site"              "Clutch"     "Date"
## [7] "Survival"         "Survperc"
```

```
attach(Overallsurvival)
```

```
boxplot(Survival~Experimentalvenue*Origin, col= gray.colors(2, alpha = 0.5),data = Overallsurvival)
```



```
detach(Overallsurvival)
```

```
survbinom=read.table('Survival binomial.txt',header=T)
names(survbinom)
```

```
## [1] "Experimentalvenue" "Origin"      "Treatment"
## [4] "Mesocosm"          "Site"       "Clutch"
## [7] "tadpole"           "Date"       "Survival"
```

```
attach(survbinom)

#Defining variables
Experimentalvenue3 <- as.factor(Experimentalvenue)
summary(Experimentalvenue3) #fixed effect
```

```
## Potchefstroom Stellenbosch
##           1500           1500
```

```
Origin3<-as.factor(Origin)
summary(Origin3)
```

```
##    P    S
## 1500 1500
```

```
Site3<-as.factor(Site)
summary(Site3) #Random effect
```

```
## BT CP JH KM LP PS
## 600 300 450 750 450 450
```

```
Clutch3<-as.factor(Clutch)
summary(Clutch3) #Nested within site
```

```
## 1 2 3
## 1200 1200 600
```

```
Treatment3<-as.factor(Treatment)
summary(Treatment3)
```

```
## PotchefstroomP PotchefstroomS StellenboschP StellenboschS
## 750 750 750 750
```

```
summary(Survival)
```

```
## Min. 1st Qu. Median Mean 3rd Qu. Max.
## 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.221 0.000 1.000
```

```
#Model selection
```

```
lsurv1<- glmer(Survival ~ Experimentalvenue3*Origin3 +(1|Site3/Clutch3), data =survbinom, na.
action = "na.pass", family= "binomial")
```

```
dredge(lsurv1)
```

```
## Fixed term is "(Intercept)"
```

	(Intercept)	Experimentalvenue3	Origin3	Experimentalvenue3:Origin3	df	logLik
	<dbl>	<fct>	<fct>	<fct>	<int>	<dbl>
8	-1.716829	+	+	+	6	-1296.135
4	-2.785670	+	+	NA	5	-1370.315
2	-2.152421	+	NA	NA	4	-1371.388
3	-2.217920	NA	+	NA	4	-1394.406
1	-1.578340	NA	NA	NA	3	-1396.112

```
5 rows | 1-8 of 10 columns
```

```
#Testing residuals
```

```
rr=simulateResiduals(lsurv1) ### simulate residuals
plotResiduals(rr) ### qqlpot simulated vs observed
```



```
testResiduals(rr)###test qqplot
```



```
## $uniformity
##
## Asymptotic one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
##
## data: simulationOutput$scaledResiduals
## D = 0.027624, p-value = 0.02054
## alternative hypothesis: two-sided
##
##
## $dispersion
##
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.
## simulated
##
## data: simulationOutput
## dispersion = 1.1206, p-value = 0.312
## alternative hypothesis: two.sided
##
##
## $outliers
##
## DHARMA outlier test based on exact binomial test with approximate
## expectations
##
## data: simulationOutput
## outliers at both margin(s) = 24, observations = 3000, p-value = 0.9182
## alternative hypothesis: true probability of success is not equal to 0.007968127
## 95 percent confidence interval:
## 0.005132282 0.011880121
## sample estimates:
## frequency of outliers (expected: 0.00796812749003984 )
##
##                                0.008
```

```
## $uniformity
##
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```

```
plotQQunif(rr, testUniformity = T) ### plot
```



```
testDispersion(rr,plot=T) ### test
```

DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs. simulated


```
##  
## DHARMA nonparametric dispersion test via sd of residuals fitted vs.  
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##  
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```

```
detach(survbinom)
```